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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, HUMAN GREED, AND THE COMMON GOOD

ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a revolutionary technology designed, *inter alia*, for smarter decision-making. The aim of technology is to alleviate human needs but human greed, the inordinate craving for accumulation of excessive wealth, power, control and fame for selfish interests, does not allow AI to ameliorate modern society for the good of all. The point at issue is, can AI be redesigned to provide solutions to global challenges such as poverty, inequality, access to good education and healthcare for all? Can it be made to bridge the yawning gap between the haves and have-nots? Can it rid society of prejudices and bridge the rifts between men and women, Whites and Blacks? Why can't AI systems be used to equalize status since human beings are born equal? The application of AI is driven by human insatiability, converting what could have been a tool for upward mobility for all to one of exploitation, and power consolidation. This paper critically examines the role of greed in shaping AI and its impact on social inequality. It argues that greed fundamentally hampers AI's potential to serve the common good and it recommends a generous application of AI.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Human Greed, Common Good, Inequality, Ethics.

INTRODUCTION

AI is undeniably the most trans-formative technology in human history. It offers new possibilities for addressing global challenges in agriculture, healthcare, and education. AI-powered systems can optimize crop yields, thereby addressing food insecurity in underdeveloped regions. In healthcare, AI's

precision in diagnosing diseases enhances patient outcomes, saving countless lives.¹ Similarly, education sector can benefit significantly from AI-driven platforms providing personalized instruction, but can the poor afford it? The immense promises of AI should be directed towards alleviating human suffering and fostering an equitable world. Or should this ideal vision be allowed to end up as virtual reality due to cupidity? With AI revolution, one expects human drudgery to be reduced to the barest minimum. If machines do most of the work, humans should have the needed time for recreation, rejuvenation and proper development. On the contrary, capitalists acquire sophisticated technologies, displace workers and widen the gap between the haves and have-nots. The ambivalent impact of technology creates an ethical dilemma. AI development must be re-imagined through relationality, justice, and accountability. However, the root of the problem is not in technology itself but in the greed that drives its application. The insatiable desire for wealth, power, and control, shapes the trajectory of AI's development and deployment. Greed manifests not only in individuals but also in institutions. Governments and corporations' priorities are centred around profit maximization and domination rather than equitable outcomes. This greed distorts the ethical purpose of AI, reducing AI to a tool for exploitation and perpetuation of inequality.

Consider recruitment algorithms driven by AI, which, instead of promoting fairness, often reflect and reinforce existing biases, marginalizing underrepresented groups leading to dehumanization.² Similarly, the monopolization of AI technology by a handful of tech giants has further widened economic disparities by concentrating wealth and opportunities in the hands of the elite. Rather than being an equalizer, AI becomes a mechanism to deepen societal divides. The Igbo proverb, "Uba zuo okè iro àlàà"— Equitable distribution of wealth eliminates animosity,³ underscores the importance of distributive justice. Whenever greed prevails, peace and collective well-being are sacrificed, undermining AI's potential as a tool for the common good.

¹ https://www.swissinfo.ch/eng/sci-tech/new-technologies_ai-has-enormous-potential-to-transform-health-sector/44123698

² Fritts, Meegan & Cabrera, Frank. (2021). AI Recruitment Algorithms and the Dehumanization Problem. *Ethics and Information Technology*. 23. 10.1007/s10676-021-09615-w, p.1.

³ Eboh, Marie Pauline, (2023) "Building Africa's Noble Future on Sound Philosophy." Eboh, M. P. & Elechi, M. (eds.), *Anthology of Authentic African Philosophy: A Revisionist View*, Bereko Multinational Ltd., Port Harcourt, p.2.

Prevailing realities provoke pressing questions that need urgent attention. Can AI truly foster equality in a world dominated by selfish interests? Is technology inherently neutral, or does it inevitably reflect the motivations of its inventors? What ethical principles must guide AI to ensure it serves humanity genuinely and holistically? Philosophical insights are critical here. Martin Heidegger, for example, emphasized that the essence of technology is in its ability to reveal truth and alleviate suffering.⁴ When technology is corrupted by greed, it ceases to fulfil this ethical mandate and instead becomes a means to perpetuate disparities.

In this paper, we argue that human greed is the primary obstacle preventing AI from fulfilling its trans-formative promise for the common good. Rather than serving as a force for collective good, greed disorients AI turning it into an instrument of power and exploitation. Addressing this challenge requires a profound re-evaluation of how AI is developed and deployed. A framework grounded in relational ontology, justice, and accountability must replace the current profit-driven paradigm. Only by doing so can AI align with humanity's aspirations for equality, progress, and shared prosperity.

According to an Igbo adage, “*The onye kuru, ka o ga aghoro*”—whatever a person sows, he will reap. AI's trajectory has shown that one cannot sow selfishness and reap benignity. Without addressing the greed that undermines its potential, AI will continue to reflect selfish interests, producing outcomes that deepen inequality rather than bridging divides. The urgent task before us is to redefine the ethical boundaries within which AI operates, ensuring it serves as a tool for collective advancement and not individual or institutional gain. This paper is significant for its clarion call for a global ethical standpoint on AI for the common good, advocating for AI as a partner in human progress, promoting equity and bridging societal gaps, and not AI as a tool for domination.

ONTOLOGY OF AI

Artificial Intelligence is fundamentally a human invention, an intricate extension of human ingenuity, values, and ambitions. At its core, AI functions as a technological manifestation of human thought and purpose. This raises the questions: what does it mean for AI to exist, and how is its nature inherently tied

⁴ [https://www.futurelearn.com/info/courses/philosophy-of-technology/0/steps/26315#:~:text=As%20we%20just%20heard%2C%20Heidegger's,3\)%20technology%20is%20%E2%80%9Cthe%20highest](https://www.futurelearn.com/info/courses/philosophy-of-technology/0/steps/26315#:~:text=As%20we%20just%20heard%2C%20Heidegger's,3)%20technology%20is%20%E2%80%9Cthe%20highest)

to human meaning? AI is neither wholly an autonomous entity nor was it created ex nihilo; it is but a dependent construct that mirrors both the nobility and stinginess of its inventors. AI, in its essence, functions as an extension of human capabilities. It is designed to perform tasks that humans find challenging, time-consuming, or impossible to achieve with natural limitations. For instance, AI systems such as OpenAI's ChatGPT demonstrate how machines can process vast amounts of data and provide insights that would take humans years to generate. These innovations reflect the inherent promise of AI: to augment human abilities and solve complex problems. It is noteworthy to emphasize that this ability is not independent but fundamentally rooted in the intentions, design, and programming of human inventors.⁵

Some think that by ascribing mental quality to technologies and AI systems, we have failed to understand their ontological status as a unique and distinct being. Thus, there is a need to redefine robots and what characterizes them.⁶ We should not be comparing AI with humans as if they are wholly independent beings, whereas they are meant to be harnessed for human improvement. According to Eboh, as technology is meant to serve human need, the role of philosophy is to guide technological development and to explain critically the pre-ontological assumptions underlying scientific enterprise, while raising fundamental questions about the object under investigation.⁷ Philosophy has the mandate to inform scientific inquiry, particularly in a field like AI, because technology is like fire in the hands of a toddler. Ethics should indicate the way this fire should be handled harmlessly. Eboh insists that there is nothing like technological determinism; technology is a human enterprise and should be controlled with human criteria both in theory and in practice.⁸

Relational ontology best sums up the nature or essence of AI technology. Relational ontology is the philosophical position that what distinguishes subject from subject, subject from object, or object from object is mutual relation rather than substance. Ontologically, substance refers to the essence or nature of a

⁵ Spitzer, Philipp, Joshua Holstein, Katelyn Morrison, Kenneth Holstein, Gerhard Satzger, and Niklas Kühl. (2024) "Don't Be Fooled: The Misinformation Effect of Explanations in Human-AI Collaboration." <https://arxiv.org/html/2409.12809v1#abstract>

⁶ Herrera Pérez, Carlos & Sanz, Ricardo. (2016). *Heideggerian AI and the Being of Robots*. 10.1007/978-3-319-26485-1_29. p. 12

⁷ M. P. Eboh (1998) *Introduction to Philosophy and Philosophizing* Enugu: Snaap Press Ltd, p.162.

⁸ Eboh (1998) *Introduction to Philosophy and Philosophizing*, p.154.

being.⁹ The relational nature of AI accentuates its dependency on human meaning. Unlike natural beings, which possess intrinsic values, AI has utilitarian value; it derives its direction and moral weight entirely from its inventors. It does not possess self-awareness or an independent capacity for moral reasoning. For instance, the algorithms that power AI systems are meticulously crafted by programmers, who embed specific objectives, biases, and limitations into the code. These algorithms are not inherently "intelligent" in a normal sense; they execute tasks based on predefined parameters.¹⁰ This dependency challenges the perception of AI as a wholly autonomous entity, positioning it instead as a reflection of human ambition.

Can AI *per se* and *in se* authentically engage with the world, or will it remain a mere tool of human aspiration? Martin Heidegger might argue that technology, including AI, functions as a means through which humans reveal their understanding of the world. Yet, this revelation is mediated by human intentions, which are sometimes conflicted. Although some may design AI for noble purposes, such as improving healthcare or combating climate change, others may exploit it for selfish gains, such as surveillance, manipulation, or profit maximization. Examples that illustrate the ambivalence purpose of AI abound. In the field of healthcare, AI has revolutionized disease diagnosis and treatment. Systems like IBM's Watson can analyse medical records and recommend treatments with incredible accuracy.¹¹ But these systems are often inaccessible to low-income earners, suggesting the socioeconomic biases of their inventors. Similarly, AI-driven recommendation algorithms on social media platforms personalize content for users, enhancing their experience. Yet, algorithms are exploited to spread misinformation, manipulate elections, and amplify divisive content.¹²

The Igbo proverb, what affects a child ultimately impacts the parent aptly captures the relational ontology of AI. Just as AI is shaped by human intentions, its impact inevitably reflects on society. When designed with care and ethical consideration, AI can serve saner purposes and uplift humanity. When driven by

⁹ Schaab, G.L. (2013). Relational Ontology. In: Runehov, A.L.C., Oviedo, L. (eds) Encyclopedia of Sciences and Religions. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8265-8_847

¹⁰ Herrera Pérez, Carlos & Sanz, Ricardo. (2016). *Heideggerian AI and the Being of Robots*. p.2

¹¹ <https://www.logicalis.com/insights/what-is-ibm-watson>

¹² <https://slate.com/technology/2022/01/ibm-watson-health-failure-artificial-intelligence.html>

selfish motives, it can exacerbate societal divides and ethical dilemmas, and ultimately afflict humanity.

The ontology of AI is inextricably linked to human dependency. It exists not as an entirely autonomous entity but as a mirror of human intentions both noble and ignoble. Addressing the critical ontological question requires an honest reflection on how humanity chooses to define and direct this trans-formative technology. Will AI remain a mere instrument of ambition, or can it evolve into a tool that authentically serves the common good? The answer is not in AI itself but in the ethical and purposeful choices of its inventors.

AI AND SOCIAL INEQUALITY

In her article: “Artificial Intelligence’s White Guy Problem”, Kate Crawford argued that AI systems in most cases inherit the prejudices of their inventors, leading to discrimination against women, racial minorities, and other marginalized groups.¹³ Rather than providing an equitable opportunity for all, algorithms serve the interests of those already in power, making it harder for disadvantaged groups to gain access to high-paying jobs. This is just one example of how greed influences the development of AI in ways that worsen inequality rather than mitigate it.

Artificial Intelligence (AI), if developed and applied ethically, holds the potential to bridge social gaps and foster an equitable society. AI’s ability to automate tasks, optimize resources, and enhance decision-making could lead to wealth creation, improved public health outcomes, and accessible opportunities for all. Should access to knowledge and resources be democratized, AI could catalyse economic inclusion. Achieving this vision of AI as a force for equality depends on commitment to ethical design and equitable distribution of AI’s benefits.

In his book, *The Republic*, Plato argues that to know the right thing leads to doing it. He emphasizes the importance of knowledge and truth in achieving justice. For Plato, justice is the harmonious organization of society, where each individual contributes according to their abilities, and resources are distributed based on needs rather than power.¹⁴ If designed to serve the common good, AI can foster a similar sense of justice by ensuring that wealth and resources are distributed fairly, and biases that perpetuate inequality are eliminated. AI’s

¹³ Crawford K. (2016). “Artificial Intelligence’s White Guy Problem”. *The New York Times*. 25(06): p.5

¹⁴ Plato. (1943). *The Republic*, New York: Books, Inc., Book IV 434a

design should be rooted in the principles of transparency, fairness, and accountability to enable AI systems make decisions that reflect the values of a just society.

AI could be a tool for promoting prosperity, peace and harmony by ensuring that all persons have access to the resources they need to live comfortably. To realize the potential of AI as a force for equality, inventors and policymakers must adhere to ethical principles that prioritize the common good. These principles include equity, transparency, and ecological consciousness. Equity refers to the fair distribution of AI's benefits and burdens across all segments of society, ensuring that marginalized communities are not excluded from the opportunities AI creates. This could include creating AI tools that are affordable and accessible to everyone, regardless of their economic status. To make this feasible, tech giants should spread out the cost of production over time so as not to suffocate the poor. They may recover costs faster by selling cheap to the whole population than by selling their products exorbitantly to a few. Transparency is essential, as it ensures that AI systems operate in ways that are understandable and accountable to the public. If AI systems are to make decisions that impact people's lives, whether in healthcare, education, or employment people must have confidence that these decisions are made in good faith without hidden agenda. Lastly, ecological consciousness is crucial in the context of AI development, as it addresses the environmental impact of AI technologies. This principle encourages the development of AI systems that promote sustainable practices, such as reducing waste, optimizing renewable energy use, and supporting environmental conservation efforts.

RESPONSIBILITY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND AI

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes more integrated into various sectors, the question of responsibility and accountability in its use becomes increasingly urgent. One of the primary ethical questions on AI is whether the technology itself can be held morally accountable for its actions, or if such responsibility lies solely with its inventors. While AI systems are becoming increasingly autonomous, they are still products of human design and programming. AI does not possess agency in the way humans do; it operates based on algorithms and data inputs provided by its developers. Therefore, the moral responsibility for AI's actions rests squarely on those who create and deploy it.

AI systems, especially those powered by machine learning, can make decisions that have significant consequences, such as determining loan eligibility, diagnosing diseases, or recommending criminal sentences. When these systems make harmful decisions, such as reinforcing racial biases or disproportionately targeting certain groups, the blame is not on the technology itself. AI, by its nature, lacks the capacity for moral reasoning or ethical judgment. It is a tool, an extension of human intentions and actions, and as such, it cannot be held morally accountable. Instead, the responsibility lies with the human designers, developers, and organizations that create, implement, and manage these systems. For instance, biased AI algorithms that lead to discrimination against women or minority groups reflect the biases embedded in the data they were trained on, which is as a result of human choice.

However, in practice, accountability in AI is sometimes murky due to the complexity of its development and deployment. When AI systems malfunction or cause harm, there is often a lack of clear accountability, especially when the actions are taken by large, anonymous corporations or government agencies. Corporations and governments frequently escape responsibility by pointing to the complexity of AI systems and their autonomy, claiming that the AI's behaviour was not anticipated or directly controlled. For example, tech giants like Facebook and Google have faced criticism for allowing their AI systems to spread misinformation or promote harmful contents, but they often avoided full responsibility, emphasizing the unpredictable nature of AI or the challenge of moderating massive platforms. In these cases, AI is treated as a black box, where the responsibility for its effects is obscured by the complexity of its underlying algorithms.

The evasion of accountability by powerful entities, especially corporations, is a result of greed, the profit-driven motives that shape AI development. When the main goal of AI development is financial gain, companies may cut corners on ethical considerations in favour of maximizing profits. In some cases, AI tools are developed with little regard for the broader societal implications, such as how they might affect human rights or deepen inequality. Thus, philosophy of science ought to play a crucial role in the development of ethical AI systems, not by dictating the technological directions but by critically examining the assumptions and ethical foundations that guide technological progress. Philosophers bring valuable perspectives on human values, ethics, and social consequences that can help developers and policymakers think through the moral implications of AI. Philosophy encourages

a deeper understanding of the ethical consequences of technological advancements and can provide frameworks for thinking about responsibility and accountability in AI.

Ethical theories such as deontology, consequentialism, and virtue ethics can be applied to the development of AI to evaluate its potential harms and benefits. Deontological ethics of Immanuel Kant, emphasizes duty and moral principles over outcomes. When applied to AI, we might argue that AI should be developed with a strong moral framework that respects human dignity and rights, regardless of the consequences. On the other hand, utilitarianism, which focuses on the greatest good for the greatest number, could lead to the development of AI that aims to maximize social welfare. However, this could also justify harmful trade-offs if the greatest good disproportionately benefits one group over others. A virtue ethics approach, which emphasizes moral character and virtues such as fairness and justice, could inspire AI development focused on fostering human flourishing and societal well-being.

Philosophers also bring attention to the social, political, and economic contexts in which AI operates. They can help question the assumptions about human nature, power dynamics, and justice that underlie AI systems. Langdon Winner's concept of "technological politics" suggests that technology is never neutral; it embodies the values and power structures of those who design and implement it.¹⁵ This means that AI systems, which are developed in the view of global capitalist and neoliberal economies, will inevitably reflect and reinforce existing power imbalances unless intentionally designed to do otherwise.

The ethical development of AI requires human accountability and transparency at every stage. AI systems should not be treated as autonomous agents that exist beyond human control; instead, they should be seen as tools that require responsible human oversight. Developers, corporations, and governments must take responsibility for the decisions AI makes and the consequences that follow. Transparency is essential in this process, as it ensures that AI systems are understandable and their decision-making processes can be scrutinized. For example, the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) includes provisions that require companies to explain how

¹⁵ Axell, C. (2019). "10 Langdon Winner: A Call for a Critical Philosophy of Technology". In *Reflections on Technology for Educational Practitioners*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004405516_010

automated decisions are made, giving individuals the right to contest decisions made by AI systems.

This move towards transparency is crucial in ensuring that AI systems are accountable to the public and that individuals are not harmed by opaque, unchecked algorithms. Moreover, ethical frameworks for AI development should be based on a commitment to justice, fairness, and equity, ensuring that AI does not perpetuate or exacerbate existing inequalities. A commitment to fairness might involve designing AI systems that minimize biases, particularly those based on race, gender, or socioeconomic status.

GREED AND AI ETHICAL DILEMMA

As AI increasingly integrates into society, the ethical dilemma of how it is used and for whose benefit has come into sharp focus. A fundamental issue is the way greed undermines AI's true potential. AI, in its essence, was presumed to augment human capabilities, alleviate suffering, and provide solutions to complex societal challenges. Yet, in practice, AI is shaped by economic and political interests that prioritize profit and power over the common good. This reduction of AI to a mere tool for financial gain compromises its purpose, leading to systems that primarily benefit the wealthy and powerful rather than the entire society. Instead of using AI to solve pressing global issues—such as poverty, climate change, or inequality—these entities often focus on how AI can increase their market share or streamline operations, sometimes at the expense of privacy, fairness, and human rights.

AI serves as a tool for exploitation rather than enlightenment, reinforcing the selfish nature of technological progress driven by profit. According to Stahl, the ethical concerns surrounding AI's commercialization are largely a result of an unregulated and profit-driven technological environment.¹⁶ Moreover, AI's role in automating labour processes exacerbates income inequality, a key consequence of greed in technology. Automation, although promising increased productivity, has displaced millions of workers, particularly in industries such as manufacturing and retail, where human labour is increasingly substituted by AI systems. As a result, companies save on labour costs but fail to address the unemployment and economic instability created by the shift. The promise of AI to improve living standards for all is, in this instance, subverted by the desire to

¹⁶ Stahl, Bernd. (2021). Ethical Issues of AI. In *Artificial Intelligence for a Better Future, An Ecosystem Perspective on the Ethics of AI and Emerging Digital Technologies*. Springer 10.1007/978-3-030-69978-9_4. p.28

maximize profits for a small group at the top. In essence, AI's benefits are hoarded by the affluent ignoring the masses. How to avert and overcome this problem is the quandary?

To overcome this ethical dilemma, it is essential to rethink AI's role in society through the framework of relational ontology. This philosophical perspective emphasizes that human beings and technology should exist in a network of interconnected relationships. In this view, AI is not merely an object or a tool to be exploited, but a partner in human progress. Such a relational approach to AI would redefine its purpose from a means of profit generation to a tool that collaborates with humans to address collective challenges.

Relational ontology suggests that AI should be designed with societal values and ethical imperatives in mind, emphasizing cooperation over competition. This shift in perspective would require AI developers and policymakers to prioritize the broader societal good over corporate interests, aligning AI development with goals such as equity, justice, and human dignity.

A prime illustration of this transformation in AI advancement is the inception of the "AI for Good" campaign by the International Telecommunication Union of the United Nations.¹⁷ This initiative promotes AI endeavours aimed at tackling global issues such as climate change, poverty, and healthcare, with a focus on ensuring the fair distribution of AI's advantages among all individuals. The initiative emphasizes the importance of ethical AI development, which considers the societal, political, and environmental repercussions of AI technologies. This strategy is in line with relational ontology, which envisions a collaborative bond between AI and humanity that prioritizes the long-term welfare of society over immediate profits.

To transform AI into a genuine catalyst for collective welfare, a global transition towards ethical AI development is imperative. This necessitates the establishment of international frameworks and policies that prioritize equity, transparency, and the ethical utilization of technology. These frameworks must be meticulously crafted to ensure that AI systems are conceived and implemented in a manner that fosters societal fairness, human integrity, and ecological longevity.

¹⁷ International Telecommunication Union, AI for Common good. Retrieved from: https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/ITU_AI_for_Good#:~:text=AI%20for%20Good%20was%20established,with%20over%2040%20UN%20agencies.

The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a pioneering example of a legal framework that seeks to regulate the use of AI in a manner that protects individuals' privacy and rights. The GDPR requires companies to provide transparency regarding the data used to train AI systems and to allow individuals to contest decisions made by AI.¹⁸ Such frameworks ensure that AI is not developed solely with profit in mind but is held to a higher standard of responsibility and accountability. This in turn should serve as model for broader global efforts to regulate AI, emphasizing the importance of human rights and fairness in AI development. In addition, global collaborations, such as the Partnership on AI, bring together stakeholders from diverse sectors, including technology, academia, government, and civil society, to create guidelines and best practices for the ethical development of AI. This type of multilateral cooperation is crucial in addressing the power imbalances that allow greed to dictate AI development and ensure that AI serves the entire humanity.

GREED HINDERS AI FOR THE COMMON GOOD

Greed is fast becoming an aspect of human nature. It has shaped society and its systems for centuries and can be understood through both historical and philosophical perspectives. Greed is defined as the relentless pursuit of self-interest to the point of harming others. Niccolò Machiavelli in his book *The Prince* argued that humans are inherently driven by a desire for power and control, and they will go to great lengths to maintain their position in society.¹⁹ This has made people to justify the vices they do, even economic pressure has lured many into doing extreme things in order to maintain their control and dominance. “And here we observe that men must either be cajoled or crushed; for they will avenge themselves for slight wrongs, while for grave ones they cannot. The injury therefore that you do to a man should be such that you need not fear his revenge.”²⁰ In a similar vein, John Locke’s theories about property rights and self-interest have been instrumentalized for accumulation at the expense of others, thence, demonstrating how greed is woven into the very fabric of capitalist societies. But Locke was particular about limits to accumulation of

¹⁸ Panel for the Future of Science and Technology. "The Impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on Artificial Intelligence." European Parliamentary Research Service, June 2020. PE 641.530. pp.35-48

¹⁹ Nicolo Machiavelli. (1952). *The Prince* in the Great Books of the Western World. Trans. W.K. Marriott and edited by Robert Maynard Hutchins, volume 23, Chicago: Encyclopedia Britannica, Inc. Ch15, 22, 76, 77.

²⁰ Niccolo Machiavelli. (1965). *The Prince*. Trans. Christian E. Detmold. New York: Airmont Publishing Company. p.18

wealth and opined that “as much as anyone can make use of any advantage of life before it spoils; so much he may by his labour fix property in. Whatever is beyond this, is more than his share, and belongs to others.”²¹ Greed, in its most destructive form, becomes a driving force that prevents individuals and societies from working toward collective good; it leads to exploitation and oppression instead. This relentless pursuit of self-interest even at the cost of others is a key barrier in AI’s potential to serve the common good.

“Common good is one of the principles of the social order, which consists in human nature. ... By being composed of body and spirit, in comparison with brutes, a person is more dependent on others for the full realization of his/her humanity.”²² AI is a powerful tool with immense potential for social good, will human greed allow it do its wonders for social solidarity? The technological advancements that AI promises such as automation, economic efficiencies, healthcare innovation are frequently exploited by powerful corporations and governments to consolidate wealth, influence, and control. Rather than using AI to bridge societal gaps, these entities often deploy it to solidify their power and amplify existing inequalities. The wealthy and powerful monopolize access to AI’s benefits, using it for economic gains and political dominance. AI is increasingly being used in surveillance technologies, predictive policing, and voter manipulation, all of which serve to protect the interests of the elite while deepening the divide between them and the marginalized.

Greed manifests in the economic sectors, the wealthy benefits from AI disproportionately and the poor languishes. Automation, which AI promises to make ubiquitous across industries, threatens to displace low-wage workers while benefiting only the owners of capital and technology. AI can optimize supply chains, reducing labour costs for companies, but it also eliminates jobs for workers who can’t easily switchover to new forms of employment. Report by the McKinsey Global Institute, corroborate that automation could displace 400 to 800 million workers worldwide by 2030.²³ This phenomenon is not happening in isolation; it is deeply intertwined with the greed-driven desire of corporations

²¹ John Locke. (1993) *Two Treatises of Government* edited by Mark Goldie. London: Everyman. Chapter 5 par. 31, 130.

²² Njoku F.O.C (2019). *Introduction to Social and Political Philosophy*. Enugu: University of Nigeria Press Ltd. p.59

²³ Manyika, J., Lund, S., Chui, M., Bughin, J., Woetzel, L., Batra, P., Ko, R., & Sanghvi, S. (2017). *Jobs lost, jobs gained: What the future of work will mean for jobs, skills, and wages*. McKinsey Global Institute.

to cut costs and maximize profits, disregarding its consequences on human beings.

In healthcare, AI could potentially save millions of lives through early disease detection and personalized treatment. However, AI's promise is monopolized by the affluent. Access to AI-powered health tools is typically restricted to those with the financial means to afford them. Wealthy nations, hospitals, and private healthcare providers reap the benefits of AI, while those in low-income regions or underfunded healthcare systems are left out. According to the World Health Organization, despite the rapid advancement of AI in medicine, the majority of low-income countries do not have the infrastructure to implement these technologies, deepening global health disparities.²⁴ Yet whenever there is 'pandemic' and viruses are manufactured, they are spread widely to reach the poor and needy wherever they are.

In education, AI holds the potential to revolutionize learning by offering personalized tutoring, adaptive learning platforms, and access to educational resources. Yet, this technology is often most accessible to affluent societies with advanced digital infrastructure. In developing countries, where educational resources are scarce, AI-driven platforms are out of reach, further entrenching the educational divide. For instance, while countries like the United States and China invest heavily in AI for educational purposes, many sub-Saharan African nations due to imperial exploitation are still struggling with access to basic educational resources, such as textbooks and qualified teachers. These instances exemplify how greed transforms AI from a tool potentially reducing inequality to an instrument of further exploitation and divisiveness. The monopolization of AI benefits by the wealthy worsens existing social and economic divides, limiting the technology's ability to create an equal and just society. The unchecked greed of powerful individuals and corporations ultimately limits AI's potential to uplift society, leaving behind those who need it the most. For AI to genuinely bridge the gap between the rich and the poor, it must be shaped by values that prioritize equity, justice, and the collective well-being of all people.

²⁴ Monlezun, D. J., Omutoko, L., Oduor, P., Kokonya, D., Rayel, J., Sotomayor, C., Girault, M. I., De los Ríos Uriarte, M. E., Sinyavskiy, O., Aksamit, T., Dugani, S. B., Garcia, A., & Gallagher, C. (2023). Health care digitization in low- and middle-income countries. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/bulletin/online-first/blt.24.291643.pdf?sfvrsn=5162049c_3

PHILOSOPHY, AI AND HUMAN GREED

The ethical purpose of technology has long been a subject of philosophical inquiry. Historically, technological tools were created with the primary intent to alleviate human suffering and improve living conditions. Early technologies, from simple stone tools to the more advanced implements of the Iron Age, were crafted to serve humanity's basic needs, whether for hunting, agriculture, or shelter. For Heidegger, the essence of technology lies in its ability to "bring forth" or "a way of revealing" the world in a way that enables human flourishing.²⁵ This idea emphasizes that technology should be a force for good, a tool that facilitates human life and promotes communal well-being. In this traditional view, tools, including AI, are meant to serve as extensions of human capability, improving our lives, productivity, and collective existence. However, the reality of modern AI development seems to diverge from this ideal. Instead of alleviating human suffering and promoting the common good, AI is often shaped by greed, used to concentrate power and control in the hands of a few. How did AI, an innovation designed to serve humanity, become a tool of exploitation?

Buber emphasized the importance of relationships in human life, particularly the "I-Thou" relationship, characterized by mutual respect, dialogue, and a recognition of the other's subjectivity. In contrast to an "I-It" relationship, where one party treats the other as an object or means to an end, an "I-Thou" relationship is one in which both parties are seen as equal participants in a shared experience.²⁶ If we apply this approach to AI, it allows us to see it not just as a tool, but as a potential partner in humanity's development. AI, when developed and used within a framework of mutual respect and collaboration, could serve to enhance human capacities, solve complex problems, and create more equitable opportunities for all.

The ascendancy of scientific pursuits in Western minds, as noted by Whitehead, has led to the development of artificial intelligence (AI) that prioritizes efficiency and profit over human well-being.²⁷ This has enabled human greed to flourish, as individuals and corporations exploit AI-driven systems to accumulate wealth and power. However, process philosophy suggests that this narrow focus on

²⁵ Heidegger, M. (1977). *The Question Concerning Technology and Other Essays*. (W. Lovitt, Trans.) Harper & Row. p. 12

²⁶ Simon, A. E. (n.d.). Martin Buber. Encyclopaedia Britannica. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Martin-Buber-German-religious-philosopher/From-mysticism-to-dialogue>

²⁷ J. R. Hustwit. Process Philosophy, Retrieved from <https://iep.utm.edu/processp/>

scientific progress and economic gain neglects the importance of aesthetics, ethics, and religion in shaping a comprehensive worldview. When we ignore these intuitions, we risk creating AI systems that perpetuate inequality, exacerbate environmental degradation, and erode human dignity. Thus, human values such as compassion, empathy, and justice will be far-fetched.

Process philosophy suggests that all entities, human and non-human, exist in a network of interconnected relationships. In this view, AI is not an isolated entity, but part of a larger web of relations that shapes and is shaped by human society. AI's development, then, should be seen as part of a dynamic process in which it plays a role in advancing human's collective progress. This relational ontology requires a shift in perspective, AI should not be viewed as merely an object to be exploited but as a partner for the common good. This view calls for the ethical imperative of using AI to benefit all people, rather than allowing it to serve the interests of a select few.

Gynist philosophy avers that if we regard everyone in the society as human beings with full rights and privileges, we will use AI innovation to uplift humanity. Accommodationist love and complementarity are of paramount importance here given that if love prevails, and people co-operate, we will not seek avenues to exploit but to edify others. This is because where love abides, people tend to see one another as brothers and sisters and spontaneous synergy springs up in the society. Mutual respect between the haves and the have-nots will aid not only the acknowledgement of the intrinsic worth of both but also their roles in maintaining equilibrium and synergy in the society. It is obvious that the greed-driven use of AI deviates from this relational norm. AI's development, when motivated by greed, becomes a tool for domination, surveillance, and control, rather than mutual collaboration. AI-driven surveillance systems, used by governments and corporations to monitor and control populations, treat individuals as mere objects, undermining the possibility of an "I-Thou" relationship. Instead of fostering a deeper understanding of human needs and values, these technologies are in most cases used to reinforce existing power structures and perpetuate inequality.

The monopolization of AI technologies by powerful tech corporations is another manifestation of greed. Companies like Google, Amazon, and Microsoft control vast amount of AI research and development, shaping its application to serve their interests. These corporations prioritize profit maximization over social responsibility, using AI to manipulate consumer behaviour, exploit labour,

and concentrate power.²⁸ AI algorithms that recommend products, news articles, or social media content are designed to keep users engaged and to maximize advertising revenue, often without regard for the social consequences of their influence on public opinion or mental health.²⁹

In a relational ontology, AI should be developed to enhance human relationships, foster understanding, and promote the welfare of all individuals. It should be designed to alleviate human suffering, and not to perpetuate social inequalities. In this sense, AI becomes a tool of ethical transformation, capable of reshaping society in ways that honour our shared humanity. This requires a paradigm shift in the manner AI is developed, moving away from profit-driven motives, in preference to a model that prioritises human dignity, social justice, and collective well-being. Emmanuel Levinas speaks to this idea when he emphasises the responsibility of the self toward the other. “Levinas asserts that the unintegratable alterity, infinity, and transcendence of the other give us unescapable and infinite responsibility for other.”³⁰ This responsibility can be understood as designing and using technology in a way that considers the needs, rights, and well-being of others. AI should not be used as a means of exploitation, but as a means of uplifting others and creating a just society. By adopting a relational, ethical framework for AI, we can re-imagine AI’s role in society and ensure that its benefits are shared equitably.

CONCLUSION

AI, when designed and deployed responsibly, has the potential to be a trans-formative tool for social good. However, its current trajectory, largely driven by greed and profit oriented motives, undermines this potential. The ethical dilemma of AI’s development lies in the way it is often exploited for power and profit, rather than being used to address pressing global challenges. To resolve this, we must embrace relational ontology, where AI is viewed not as a tool for selfish gain, but as a partner in human progress, designed according to

²⁸ Hanley, D. A., & von Thun, M. (2024, November 12). It's not too late to stop the monopolization of AI. Retrieved from: <https://inequality.org/article/its-not-too-late-to-stop-the-monopolization-of-ai/>

²⁹ Asthana, R. (2023). Recommendation AI in social media: Consequences and mitigations (Bachelor's thesis, University of Virginia). Retrieved from: https://libraetd.lib.virginia.edu/downloads/g158bj79c?filename=Prospectus_Asthana_Raj_2023_BS.pdf

³⁰ Chen, H., & Hung, R. E. (2012). Levinas’ Ethics of Responsibility-for-the-other and its Implications for Ecological Thinking. Retrieved from: pesa.org.au

ethical imperatives and societal values. Then we can speak of trustworthy AI.³¹ Additionally, global ethical frameworks and policies must be implemented to ensure that AI serves the common good, promoting fairness, equity, and sustainability. By addressing these ethical concerns, we can ensure that AI fulfils the goal of enhancing human life and respecting our shared values thereby manifesting accommodationist love.

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³¹https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trustworthy_AI